

FEEDBACK

workgroup	Name	E-mail	Response	
8	Olaf Rieß	olaf.riess@med.uni-tuebingen.de	no additional standards as I can see from the RD field	
8	TARTAGLIA , Marco	marco.tartaglia@opbg.net	Olaf responded	
9	TONON, giovanni	tonon.giovanni@hsr.it		
10	METSPALU, Andres	andres.metspalu@ut.ee	.	
10	PEROLA, Markus	markus.perola@thl.fi	.	
11	SCHERER, Andreas	andreas.scherer@helsinki.fi	I am trying to get a response for WG11, but there are questions about who the "Reviewers of the minimal dataset" are, and what exactly to respond in the columns. Do you have any further instructions as to how to fill this in? 2023-08-03: Janne Vehreschild (UzK) <vehrescj@uni-koeln.de> replied that there are no comments, and that the document looks good.	action: further instructions sent by email
12	UITTERLINDEN , André	a.g.utterlinden@erasmusmc.nl	.	

